

RECOGNIZED IN "Y"
CATEGORY BY

Research Consortium Archive

P(ISSN) : 3007-0031

E(ISSN) : 3007-004X

<https://rc-archive.com/index.php/Journal/about>

Exploring the Drivers of Antimicrobial Resistance in Rural Communities: Challenges and Solutions

Anchal Kumari

Liaquat National Medical College, Karachi, Sindh, Pakistan

Hira Jamil

Department of Pharmacy Practice, Faculty of Pharmacy, Jinnah University for Women, Karachi, Pakistan

Abdul Razzaque Nohri*

Health Department, Government of Sindh, Pakistan. Corresponding Author Email:

razaquenohri@gmail.com

Kirsh Kumar

Jinnah Sindh Medical University, Karachi, Sindh, Pakistan

Sajan Sarang

Health Department, Government of Sindh, Pakistan

Hina Qasim Memon

Health Department, Government of Sindh, Pakistan

Publisher : EDUCATION GENIUS SOLUTIONS

Review Type: Double Blind Peer Review

ABSTRACT

Background: Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a growing global health crisis, with rural communities facing a heightened burden due to inadequate healthcare access and weak regulation of antibiotic use. In Pakistan, easy over-the-counter availability and widespread misuse of antibiotics are major contributors to resistance. **Objective:** To identify the drivers of AMR in rural communities and examine the relationship between antibiotic use behaviors and the presence of resistant bacteria. **Methods:** A cross-sectional study was conducted among 120 residents of selected rural areas. Data were collected using structured questionnaires to capture demographic characteristics, antibiotic use patterns, and accessibility factors. Laboratory reports on collected samples were analyzed to detect resistant bacteria. Descriptive statistics summarized key variables, and chi-square tests assessed associations between behavioral factors and resistance, with significance set at $p < 0.05$. **Results:** Of the respondents, 61.7% reported self-medicating with antibiotics, 100% could obtain antibiotics without a prescription, and 56.7% did not complete their treatment course. Antibiotic use for viral illnesses was reported by 66.7% of participants. Statistically significant associations were found between self-medication and resistance detection ($p = 0.013$), purchase without prescription and resistance ($p = 0.024$), and incomplete antibiotic course and resistance ($p = 0.004$). Resistance was detected in 58.8% of those with incomplete courses, compared to 23.1% among those completing treatment. **Conclusion:** Inappropriate antibiotic use in rural communities is strongly linked to AMR, highlighting the urgent need for stricter regulations, community awareness programs, and improved rural healthcare services.

Keywords: Antimicrobial Resistance, Self-Medication, Rural Health, Prescription Regulation, Public Awareness

Introduction

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is widely recognized as one of the most urgent public health threats of the 21st century. It occurs when microorganisms such as bacteria, viruses, fungi, and parasites evolve to resist the effects of antimicrobial agents, rendering standard treatments ineffective and leading to persistent infections, increased morbidity, and higher mortality rates. Globally, an estimated 4.95 million deaths were associated with AMR in 2019, including 1.27 million directly attributable deaths.¹ Without effective interventions, it is projected that AMR could cause up to 10 million deaths annually by 2050, potentially surpassing the mortality burden of cancer. The economic repercussions are equally severe, with the World Bank forecasting substantial losses in global GDP and millions pushed into poverty as a result of the AMR crisis.²

The drivers of AMR are multifaceted, encompassing inappropriate use of antimicrobials in human medicine, veterinary practices,

agriculture, and aquaculture, compounded by inadequate infection prevention, limited diagnostic capabilities, and weak regulatory oversight. Low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), such as Pakistan, bear a disproportionate share of the burden due to fragile health systems, limited public awareness, and widespread non-prescription antibiotic use³. In Pakistan, the prevalence of AMR has been rising steadily despite the introduction of the National Action Plan (NAP) on AMR. Between 2000 and 2015, antibiotic consumption increased by 65%, making Pakistan the fourth highest consumer among LMICs. Alarming, there has been a marked increase in the use of “Watch” and “Reserve” antibiotics, including those critical for managing multidrug-resistant infections, often without prescription or diagnostic justification.⁴

Rural communities in Pakistan face distinct challenges in AMR containment. With nearly two-thirds of the population residing in rural areas, primary healthcare services are often limited to basic facilities with inadequate infection prevention and control measures. Overprescription by healthcare providers, compounded by poor adherence to clinical guidelines, further accelerates resistance development.⁵ Easy access to antibiotics over the counter, coupled with a strong culture of self-medication, contributes significantly to inappropriate antimicrobial use. Moreover, the lack of affordable diagnostic facilities encourages empirical and often excessive use of broad-spectrum antibiotics.⁶

The agricultural sector adds another dimension to the AMR problem in rural Pakistan. The livestock industry, a major contributor to rural livelihoods, frequently relies on antimicrobials for disease prevention and growth promotion.⁷ Studies have reported that up to 70% of antimicrobials in Pakistan are used in animals, with broiler chicken production alone consuming hundreds of tons annually. These practices not only increase the risk of resistant bacteria in animals but also enable transmission to humans through direct contact, contaminated food, and environmental pathways.⁸

Despite the development of Pakistan’s NAP on AMR, implementation remains inconsistent, particularly in rural areas. Barriers include insufficient funding, lack of trained personnel, weak enforcement of regulations, and limited intersectoral coordination. Surveillance systems are underdeveloped, and the “One Health” approach integrating human, animal, and environmental health perspectives has yet to be fully operationalized outside urban centers.⁹

Addressing AMR in rural communities requires a comprehensive and context-specific approach. Key priorities include improving public awareness, strengthening healthcare provider training, regulating antimicrobial sales, expanding diagnostic services, and enhancing infection prevention in both human healthcare and animal husbandry.¹⁰ Sustainable solutions also demand collaboration between public health authorities,

agricultural stakeholders, and community organizations. Lessons from successful local and international interventions suggest that integrated “One Health” strategies, tailored to the socio-economic and cultural realities of rural populations, can significantly reduce AMR risks.¹¹

This study aims to investigate the different drivers of antimicrobial resistance in rural communities of Pakistan, assess existing prevention and control measures, and propose sustainable, context-specific strategies for reducing AMR risks.

Methods

A cross-sectional survey was conducted in rural areas, focusing on households, local pharmacies, and healthcare facilities. Data were collected on the frequency and reasons for antibiotic use, such as self-medication, improper dosages, and the purchase of antibiotics without prescriptions. The availability of antibiotics in both formal healthcare settings and informal drug stores was also assessed. In addition, laboratory tests from healthcare facilities were also analyzed to determine the presence of resistant bacteria and their correlation with antibiotic usage patterns.

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data on antibiotic use and resistance, including frequency distributions and averages. The study also evaluated the association between the availability of antibiotics without prescriptions and the prevalence of resistant bacteria in the community.

Results

A total of 120 respondents from rural communities participated in the study. The findings are presented according to the study objectives, covering demographic characteristics, patterns of antibiotic use, accessibility of antibiotics, and associations with antimicrobial resistance indicators.

The demographic profile of the respondents is presented in Table 1. The largest age group was 31–45 years (40.0%), followed by 18–30 years (35.0%), and more than 45 years (25.0%). Females constituted a slight majority (55.0%). Nearly half of the respondents (48.3%) had no formal education, while 30.0% had completed primary education, and only 21.7% had attained secondary or higher education. Farming and livestock keeping were the most common occupations (36.7%), followed by homemaking (31.7%), skilled labor (26.6%), and other occupations (5.0%).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents (n = 120)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age group (years)	18-30	42	35.0
	31-45	48	40.0
	>45	30	25.0
Gender	Male	54	45.0
	Female	66	55.0
Education	No formal education	58	48.3

level	Primary	36	30.0
	Secondary or higher	26	21.7
Occupation	Farmer/livestock keeper	44	36.7
	Skilled labor	32	26.6
	Homemaker	38	31.7
	Other	6	5.0

Antibiotic usage patterns within the previous six months are summarized in Table 2. Self-medication was highly prevalent, reported by 61.7% of respondents. Only 38.3% reported obtaining antibiotics exclusively with a prescription. Nearly half (43.3%) had used leftover antibiotics from a previous illness, and more than half (56.7%) did not complete the full course of prescribed antibiotics. Inappropriate antibiotic use for viral illnesses, such as the common cold, was reported by two-thirds of respondents (66.7%).

Table 2: Patterns of Antibiotic Use in the Past 6 Months

Pattern of Use	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Used antibiotics with prescription	46	38.3
Self-medicated with antibiotics	74	61.7
Used leftover antibiotics from previous illness	52	43.3
Did not complete prescribed antibiotic course	68	56.7
Used antibiotics for viral illnesses (e.g., cold)	80	66.7

Pattern of Antibiotic Use in Past 6 Months

Table 3 outlines the accessibility of antibiotics in rural communities. Licensed pharmacies/with qualified person were the main source of antibiotics (48.3%), followed by unlicensed stores/without qualified person (36.7%) and healthcare facilities (15.0%). All participants (100%) reported that antibiotics could be obtained without a prescription. In terms of physical access, 53.3% could obtain antibiotics within 15 minutes of travel, 30.0% required 15-30 minutes, and 16.7% needed more than 30 minutes.

Table 3: Accessibility and Procurement of Antibiotics

Accessibility Factor	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Source of antibiotics	Licensed pharmacy	58	48.3
	Unlicensed store	44	36.7
	Healthcare facility	18	15.0
Antibiotics available without prescription	Yes	120	100
	No	0	0
Travel time to obtain antibiotics	< 15 minutes	64	53.3
	15-30 minutes	36	30.0
	> 30 minutes	20	16.7

The associations between selected behavioral drivers and laboratory-confirmed resistant bacteria are presented in Table 4. Self-medication was significantly associated with the presence of resistant bacteria ($\chi^2 = 6.21$, $p = 0.013$), with resistance detected in 51.4% of self-medicating respondents compared to 30.4% of those who did not self-medicate. Similarly, purchasing antibiotics without a prescription was significantly linked to resistance ($\chi^2 = 5.07$, $p = 0.024$), with resistance found in 45.7% of these individuals versus 10.7% among those obtaining antibiotics with a prescription. The strongest association was observed for incomplete antibiotic courses ($\chi^2 = 8.16$, $p = 0.004$), with resistance present in 58.8% of such cases compared to 23.1% among those who completed treatment.

Table 4: Association Between Key Drivers and Presence of Resistant Bacteria

Variable	Resistant Bacteria Detected (%)	No Resistance Detected (%)	χ^2 (p-value)
Self-medication with antibiotics	Yes: 38 (51.4%)	36 (48.6%)	6.21 (0.013)
	No: 14 (30.4%)	32 (69.6%)	
Purchase without prescription	Yes: 42 (45.7%)	50 (54.3%)	5.07 (0.024)
	No: 3 (10.7%)	25 (89.3%)	
Incomplete antibiotic course	Yes: 40 (58.8%)	28 (41.2%)	8.16 (0.004)
	No: 12 (23.1%)	40 (76.9%)	

Discussion

This study explored the key drivers of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in rural communities, focusing on patterns of antibiotic use, accessibility, and behavioral practices contributing to the spread of resistance. The findings reveal that inappropriate antibiotic practices—particularly self-medication, purchase without prescription, and incomplete treatment courses—are both common and significantly associated with the occurrence of resistant bacteria in the studied population.

A majority of respondents reported self-medicating with antibiotics (61.7%), often without medical guidance. This aligns with evidence from many low- and middle-income countries, where limited healthcare access, cost constraints, and weak regulatory enforcement facilitate easy over-the-counter antibiotic availability.¹² Such patterns create ideal conditions for the selection and spread of resistant strains, as individuals may use antibiotics unnecessarily, select inappropriate drug classes, or discontinue therapy prematurely.¹³

The study also found that antibiotics could be obtained without a prescription from any store. This observation reflects widespread gaps in pharmaceutical regulation and enforcement in rural settings.¹⁴ Similar patterns have been documented globally, particularly where unlicensed drug vendors and informal healthcare providers operate with minimal oversight. The continued sale of antibiotics outside legal frameworks undermines stewardship programs and encourages indiscriminate use.¹⁵

Incomplete antibiotic courses were another significant factor associated with the presence of resistant bacteria, with nearly 59% of those who failed to complete treatment exhibiting resistance. This supports the well-established understanding that partial treatment exposes bacteria to sublethal drug concentrations, promoting the survival and multiplication of resistant organisms.¹⁶ Such practices are frequently linked to misconceptions about symptom resolution, lack of awareness about the importance of completing therapy, and economic limitations.¹⁷

The high prevalence of antibiotic use for viral illnesses, such as colds, further highlights a critical gap in public understanding of appropriate antimicrobial indications. Treating viral infections with antibiotics offers no therapeutic benefit and only accelerates the development of resistance. This practice is widely reported in rural areas globally, where diagnostic facilities are scarce and empiric treatment is the norm.¹⁸

Accessibility patterns in this study reveal that nearly half of the respondents obtained antibiotics from licensed pharmacies, but a considerable proportion relied on unlicensed stores. This dual-channel supply structure reflects both geographic convenience and entrenched consumer trust in informal outlets.¹⁹ While licensed pharmacies may provide some degree of professional oversight, unlicensed sources lack any obligation to follow prescribing guidelines, increasing the risk of misuse.²⁰

The association between inappropriate practices and resistance detection in this study echoes findings from numerous community-based investigations, which consistently show that non-prescription use, poor adherence, and overuse of broad-spectrum antibiotics are major contributors to AMR.²¹ The detection of statistically significant relationships between these behaviors and resistance strengthens the evidence for targeted interventions in rural contexts.²²

Targeted public education, stricter regulation of antibiotic sales, and improved rural healthcare infrastructure are essential to curb inappropriate antimicrobial use, reduce resistance rates, and support sustainable AMR containment strategies in rural communities.

The study's cross-sectional design limits causal inference, and reliance on self-reported antibiotic use may introduce recall bias. Findings are specific to selected rural areas, limiting generalizability to all regions.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that inappropriate antibiotic practices particularly self-medication, purchase without prescription, and incomplete treatment are widespread in rural communities and significantly associated with antimicrobial resistance. Strengthening prescription regulations, enhancing public awareness, and improving rural healthcare access are essential to curbing AMR.

References

1. Salam MA, Al-Amin MY, Salam MT, Pawar JS, Akhter N, Rabaan AA, Alqumber MAA. Antimicrobial Resistance: A Growing Serious Threat for Global Public Health. *Healthcare (Basel)*. 2023 Jul 5;11(13):1946. doi: 10.3390/healthcare11131946. PMID: 37444780; PMCID: PMC10340576.
2. de Kraker ME, Stewardson AJ, Harbarth S. Will 10 Million People Die a Year due to Antimicrobial Resistance by 2050? *PLoS Med*. 2016 Nov 29;13(11):e1002184. doi:

- 10.1371/journal.pmed.1002184. PMID: 27898664; PMCID: PMC5127510.
3. Tang KWK, Millar BC, Moore JE. Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR). *Br J Biomed Sci.* 2023 Jun 28;80:11387. doi: 10.3389/bjbs.2023.11387. PMID: 37448857; PMCID: PMC10336207.
 4. Mirha HT, Ali SH, Aamar H, Sadiq M, Tharwani ZH, Habib Z, Malikzai A. The impact of antibiotic resistance on the rampant spread of infectious diseases in Pakistan: Insights from a narrative review. *Health Sci Rep.* 2024 Apr 22;7(4):e2050. doi: 10.1002/hsr2.2050. PMID: 38655423; PMCID: PMC11035969.
 5. Torumkuney D, Jamil B, Nizamuddin S, van Hasselt J, Pirzada U, Manenzhe R. Country data on AMR in Pakistan in the context of community-acquired respiratory tract infections: links between antibiotic susceptibility, local and international antibiotic prescribing guidelines, access to medicine and clinical outcome. *J Antimicrob Chemother.* 2022 Sep 6;77(Suppl_1):i18-i25. doi: 10.1093/jac/dkac213. PMID: 36065729; PMCID: PMC9445852.
 6. Muteeb G, Rehman MT, Shahwan M, Aatif M. Origin of Antibiotics and Antibiotic Resistance, and Their Impacts on Drug Development: A Narrative Review. *Pharmaceuticals (Basel).* 2023 Nov 15;16(11):1615. doi: 10.3390/ph16111615. PMID: 38004480; PMCID: PMC10675245.
 7. Habiba UE, Khan A, Mmbaga EJ, Green IR, Asaduzzaman M. Use of antibiotics in poultry and poultry farmers- a cross-sectional survey in Pakistan. *Front Public Health.* 2023 Jul 11;11:1154668. doi: 10.3389/fpubh.2023.1154668. PMID: 37497033; PMCID: PMC10366442.
 8. Mohsin M, Van Boeckel TP, Saleemi MK, Umair M, Naseem MN, He C, Khan A, Laxminarayan R. Excessive use of medically important antimicrobials in food animals in Pakistan: a five-year surveillance survey. *Glob Health Action.* 2019;12(sup1):1697541. doi: 10.1080/16549716.2019.1697541. PMID: 31795863; PMCID: PMC6896466.
 9. Abbas S. The challenges of implementing infection prevention and antimicrobial stewardship programs in resource-constrained settings. *Antimicrob Steward Healthc Epidemiol.* 2024 Apr 16;4(1):e45. doi: 10.1017/ash.2024.35. PMID: 38628374; PMCID: PMC11019578.
 10. Salam MA, Al-Amin MY, Salam MT, Pawar JS, Akhter N, Rabaan AA, Alqumber MAA. Antimicrobial Resistance: A Growing Serious Threat for Global Public Health. *Healthcare (Basel).* 2023 Jul 5;11(13):1946. doi: 10.3390/healthcare11131946. PMID: 37444780; PMCID: PMC10340576.
 11. Abakar MF, Seli D, Lechthaler F, Crump L, Mancus A, Tran N, Zinsstag J, Muñoz DC. Evaluation of the feasibility and sustainability of the joint human and animal vaccination and its integration to the public health system in the Danamadji health district, Chad. *Health Res Policy Syst.* 2021 Aug 11;19(Suppl

- 2):44. doi: 10.1186/s12961-021-00688-z. PMID: 34380491; PMCID: PMC8356365.
12. Gebregziabher NK, Netsereab TB, Franchesko BT, Ghebreamlak HH, Yihdego NM. Prevalence of self-medication practices with antibiotics and associated factors among students in five colleges in Eritrea: a cross-sectional study. *Antimicrob Resist Infect Control*. 2024 Sep 19;13(1):106. doi: 10.1186/s13756-024-01466-6. PMID: 39300551; PMCID: PMC11414089.
 13. Chinemerem Nwobodo D, Ugwu MC, Oliseloke Anie C, Al-Ouqaili MTS, Chinedu Ikem J, Victor Chigozie U, Saki M. Antibiotic resistance: The challenges and some emerging strategies for tackling a global menace. *J Clin Lab Anal*. 2022 Sep;36(9):e24655. doi: 10.1002/jcla.24655. Epub 2022 Aug 10. PMID: 35949048; PMCID: PMC9459344.
 14. Al Masud A, Walpola RL, Sarker M, Kabir A, Asaduzzaman M, Islam MS, Mostafa AT, Akhtar Z, Barua M, Seale H. Understanding antibiotic purchasing practices in community pharmacies: A potential driver of emerging antimicrobial resistance. *Explor Res Clin Soc Pharm*. 2024 Jul 31;15:100485. doi: 10.1016/j.rcsop.2024.100485. PMID: 39318500; PMCID: PMC11419887.
 15. Wall S. Prevention of antibiotic resistance - an epidemiological scoping review to identify research categories and knowledge gaps. *Glob Health Action*. 2019 Dec 13;12(1):1756191. doi: 10.1080/16549716.2020.1756191. PMID: 32475304; PMCID: PMC7782542.
 16. Huemer M, Mairpady Shambat S, Brugger SD, Zinkernagel AS. Antibiotic resistance and persistence-Implications for human health and treatment perspectives. *EMBO Rep*. 2020 Dec 3;21(12):e51034. doi: 10.15252/embr.202051034. Epub 2020 Dec 8. PMID: 33400359; PMCID: PMC7726816.
 17. Choudhry FR, Mani V, Ming LC, Khan TM. Beliefs and perception about mental health issues: a meta-synthesis. *Neuropsychiatr Dis Treat*. 2016 Oct 31;12:2807-2818. doi: 10.2147/NDT.S111543. PMID: 27826193; PMCID: PMC5096745.
 18. Llor C, Bjerrum L. Antimicrobial resistance: risk associated with antibiotic overuse and initiatives to reduce the problem. *Ther Adv Drug Saf*. 2014 Dec;5(6):229-41. doi: 10.1177/2042098614554919. PMID: 25436105; PMCID: PMC4232501.
 19. Hafez H, Rakab MS, Elshehaby A, Gebreel AI, Hany M, BaniAmer M, Sajed M, Yunis S, Mahmoud S, Hamed M, Abdellatif M, Alomari AN, Moqbel AE, El-Sayed OS, Elshenawy M, Tolba M, Saeed M. Pharmacies and use of antibiotics: a cross sectional study in 19 Arab countries. *Antimicrob Resist Infect Control*. 2024 Sep 18;13(1):104. doi: 10.1186/s13756-024-01458-6. PMID: 39294829; PMCID: PMC11412015.
 20. Hareem A, Lee J, Stupans I, Park JS, Wang K. Benefits and barriers associated with e-prescribing in community pharmacy - A

- systematic review. *Explor Res Clin Soc Pharm.* 2023 Nov 25;12:100375. doi: 10.1016/j.rcsop.2023.100375. PMID: 38145236; PMCID: PMC10746557.
21. Muteeb G, Rehman MT, Shahwan M, Aatif M. Origin of Antibiotics and Antibiotic Resistance, and Their Impacts on Drug Development: A Narrative Review. *Pharmaceuticals (Basel).* 2023 Nov 15;16(11):1615. doi: 10.3390/ph16111615. PMID: 38004480; PMCID: PMC10675245.
 22. Portela Dos Santos O, Melly P, Hilfiker R, Giacomino K, Perruchoud E, Verloo H, Pereira F. Effectiveness of Educational Interventions to Increase Skills in Evidence-Based Practice among Nurses: The EDITcare Systematic Review. *Healthcare (Basel).* 2022 Nov 2;10(11):2204. doi: 10.3390/healthcare10112204. PMID: 36360544; PMCID: PMC9691114.